

A Doherty Power Amplifier Based on the Harmonic Generating Mechanism

M.Sajedin¹, I.T.E.Elfergani¹, J.Rodriguez¹, R.A.Abd-Alhameed², A.M.Abdulkhaleq³, N.O.Parchin⁴, Y.I. A. Al-Yasir⁴

¹ Instituto de Telecomunicações, Aveiro, Portugal, Maryam.sajedin*, i.t.e.elfergani, jonathan@av.it.pt

² Faculty of Engineering and Informatics, Bradford University, Bradford BD7 1DP, UK, r.a.abd@bradford.ac.uk

³ SARAS Technology Limited, Leeds LS12 4NQ, UK; A.ABD@sarastech.co.uk

⁴ Electrical Engineering and Computer Science University of Bradford, Bradford, UK, N.OjaroudiParchin, Y.i.a.al-yasir@Bradford.ac.uk

Abstract— This Paper presents an energy-efficient asymmetrical Doherty amplifier based on the harmonic-tuned Class-F and Class-F⁻¹ mode of operations. In addition, the design procedure of multi-resonant circuits tuned for second and third harmonics at the device input/output are explored. The saturated Doherty architecture is designed by 10W GaN HEMT device from CREE at 3.6GHz and power added efficiency of 50% at 8dB back-off and 55% at maximum output power of 43dBm have been achieved. This superposition performance has been confirmed by comparing the simulated results with that of conventional one.

Index Terms—Switching power amplifier, Doherty power amplifier, GaN HEMT.

I. INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of 5G targeting advanced use-cases and expanded carrier aggregation to enable very high speed connectivity. Energy efficient Power Amplifier (PA) has become one of the most important requirements where the power supply is limited [1]. One of the best methods in maximizing the PA efficiency is through waveform engineering of current and voltage in the quantified manner. This improves the output power at the fundamental and reduces the DC power consumption by controlling the current conduction angle and load impedances. A great deal of interest has been focused on the harmonic generating scheme based on the network configuration, such as Class-F and inverse Class-F [2]. These amplifiers apply multiple resonators for precise tuning of device output harmonics in order to minimize the power dissipation. Several contributions have been presented in literature to study high efficiency switching mode power amplifiers at the high frequencies. Paolo Colantonio [3] focused on device input and output nonlinearities that impose limitations on the Class-F behavior and applied a full nonlinear device model for design process. The nonlinear operational behavior of the Class-F and inverse Class-F PAs are investigated in [4]. On the other hand, the nonlinearity of Class-F PA makes it unsuitable to directly replaced by linear power amplifiers in WCDMA transmitters. In this respect, several topologies have been proposed [5] to employing Class-F PA in advanced design techniques such as Doherty architecture to obtain an efficient and linear operation. Doherty PA is appealing for 5G technology due to tunable efficiency characteristic and wide aggregated bandwidth. In other work [6], the theoretical analysis of an

asymmetrical class-F/F⁻¹Doherty Power Amplifier (DPA) is carried out as a function of input voltage to compensate the low current drive of the conventional DPA.

This work provides a review on the principle of the Class-F and inverse Class-F and a useful guideline for optimum design of the harmonic terminating scheme. Then, propose a high efficiency GaN HEMT saturated DPA using distributed-type harmonic control circuit at 3.6 GHz for 5G mobile communication. The paper is organized in the following Sections. In Section II voltage and current waveforms and efficiency of Class-F and Class-F⁻¹ are described. In Section III, the design consideration and simulation results of Class-F/F⁻¹ are investigated. Next, by employing of Class F/F⁻¹ in load modulation technique a saturated Doherty using a commercial 10-W GaN device is provided in Section IV. Finally, Some conclusion remarks at the end in Section V.

II. BEHAVIOR OF CLASS-F AND CLASS-F⁻¹ AMPLIFIERS

A. Basic operation of Class-F PA

The field effect transistor is a voltage controlled current source and controlled by an input gate-source voltage. The conduction angle intrinsically determines the shape of drain current. However, with the increases of conduction angle to class A mode, the shaping effects on harmonic components is weaker. In the Class-F mode, it is assumed that the third harmonic is open circuited and delivers no third harmonic current component, however, arbitrary current component at the intrinsic try to flow to the ground because of infinite impedance. While the input voltage decreases to be lower than turn-on voltage of transistor, or the device is off, no third harmonic current is generated at all.

Fig. 1. A simplified analytical model of a FET.

Second and third harmonics have the most contribution on shaping of current and voltage waveforms and higher order of harmonics are impractical suggestion. Therefore, the current waveform of a Class-F PA is developed by DC, fundamental and second harmonic and during the interval of $0 < \omega t \leq \pi$, the transistor is conducting current and the current $i(\omega t)$ flowing through the device can be written as:

$$i(\omega t) = I_0 + i_{2nd}(2\pi\omega t) + I_R \sin(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

Where I_R is the amplitude and I_0 is the dc current component. During the interval $\pi < \omega t \leq 2\pi$, the switch is open and the transistor is in cutoff mode and the current $i(\omega t + \pi)$ is equal to zero resulting in:

$$0 = I_0 + i_{2nd}(2\pi\omega t) - I_R \sin(\omega t) \quad (2)$$

Consequently, the drain current flowing can be given by:

$$i(\omega t) = 2I_R \sin(\omega t) \quad (3)$$

Which means that the current amplitude during the interval $0 < \omega t \leq 2\pi$ is twice the fundamental current amplitude. The summation of the fundamental and second harmonic approximates a half-sinusoidal waveform, as can be seen in Fig. 2(b). The dc and fundamental current component can be expressed by equation (4) and (5), using Fourier analysis.

$$I_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\pi 2I_R \sin \omega t d\omega t = \frac{2I_R}{\pi} \quad (4)$$

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi 2I_R \sin^2 \omega t d\omega t = I_R \quad (5)$$

By driving input sinusoidal waveform, the current waveform can be approximated by half sin wave at the drain of transistor.

The aim of shaping voltage waveform in Class-F PA is to improve the fundamental voltage component for higher output power and larger gain. Fourier indicates that the combination of odd harmonics approximates the square waveform and transistor acts like a closed switch, when it goes on the compression mode. In this regard, the voltage waveform, is composed by DC voltage (V_{cc}), fundamental voltage $v_R = I_R R_L$ and third harmonic voltage components:

$$V(\omega t) = V_{cc} - V_{3rd}[(2\pi + 1)\omega t] - v_R(\omega t) \quad (5)$$

When the fundamental and third harmonic voltage components are out of phase to flatten the waveform as it is shown Fig. 2(a). By introducing a phase shift of π , equation (5) can be rewrite as:

$$V(\omega t) = 2V_{cc} - v(\omega t + \pi) \quad (6)$$

It should be noticed that the maximum value of drain voltage cannot exceed the value of $2V_{cc}$.

Fig. 2. Drain current (a) and voltage (b) time domain waveforms in Class-F PA.

The square voltage waveform pulls the current out of saturation and enhances the fundamental voltage component. In other words, the fundamental frequency amplitude has been increased by using the third harmonic component that leading to an increase in output power. When the DC power dissipation is unaffected by the third harmonic flattening, that results in the enhancement of the drain efficiency. The fundamental voltage component can be formulated by:

$$V_R = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_\pi^{2\pi} 2V_{cc} \sin(\omega t + \pi) d\omega t = \frac{4V_{cc}}{\pi} \quad (7)$$

Then the dc power and output power at the operating frequency are expressed by:

$$P_0 = V_{cc} I_0 = \frac{2V_{cc} I_R}{\pi} \quad (8)$$

$$P_1 = \frac{V_R I_1}{2} = \frac{2V_{cc} I_R}{\pi} \quad (9)$$

When there is no overlap between current and voltage simultaneously, a reduction in internal dissipated power is obtained and such a condition corresponds to a Class-F operation with 100% drain efficiency.

B. Basic operation of Class-F⁻¹

In inverse Class-F PA the drain voltage and current waveforms are interchanged and the drain current is constructed by the fundamental and odd harmonics, shaping the rectangular waveform. The drain current and voltage waveforms can be obtained by:

$$i(\omega t) = 2I_0 - i(\omega t + \pi) \quad (10)$$

$$v(\omega t) = V_R(\sin \omega t + |\sin \omega t|) \quad (11)$$

Where the V_R is the fundamental frequency amplitude. Similar to drain voltage analysis of Class-F PA, the maximum drain current cannot exceed $2I_0$. Since the drain current is zero when the transistor is off, the current waveform is made by dc, fundamental and third harmonic components where, the fundamental current can be calculated using Eq. (10) from:

$$I_1 = I_R = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\pi}^{2\pi} 2I_0 \sin(\omega t + \pi) d\omega t = \frac{4I_0}{\pi} \quad (12)$$

And the dc voltage and fundamental voltage component by taking into account Eq (11), can be written as:

$$V_{CC} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{\pi} 2V_R \sin \omega t d\omega t = \frac{2V_R}{\pi} \quad (13)$$

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} 2V_R \sin^2 \omega t d\omega t = V_R \quad (14)$$

The ratio between output power and dc at the fundamental can be given by:

$$P_1 = P_0 = \frac{V_1 I_1}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pi V_{CC}}{2} \frac{4I_0}{\pi} \quad (15)$$

In the Class-F mode, the third harmonic is optimized to maximize the output power and efficiency, when the second harmonic is nulled, on the other hand, the second harmonic is selected to improve the efficiency in the inverse Class-F PA. Therefore, by properly varying the fundamental and harmonic impedances, the fundamental voltage and current can be enhanced as the power level increases. At the high power levels, the inverse Class-F operates as a saturated amplifier with the half-rectified current waveform at intrinsic current-generator plane, however, in Class-F PA due to the third harmonic voltage component the amplifier operates as a switch in the saturation region. In addition, the inverse Class-F PA needs to be implemented by wide bandgap semiconductor technologies with large voltage swing due to its higher peak voltage than that of Class-F PA [7]. On the contrary, the fundamental current of the Class-F⁻¹ configuration is lower than that of the Class-F which makes it suitable for big device size with small fundamental impedance.

III. CLASS-F / F⁻¹ AMPLIFIERS DESIGN PROCESS

In order to maximize the Power Added Efficiency (PAE) and output power, the first step to design, is to find the optimum load and source impedances by executing the load/source pull simulation. In this regard, the initial load impedances for second and third harmonics are set to the short and open circuited respectively for Class-F PA, which should be inverse in Class-F⁻¹ mode. After adjusting the fundamental load impedance that compromises between maximum PAE and output power, then the additional load/source pull simulations are executed for optimum harmonic impedances at the input and output to enable the device to see the corresponding increases in efficiency.

In this work, design of Class-F and Class-F⁻¹ is based on the 10 W GaN HEMT, a packaged device from CREE with 28V drain voltage at 3.6GHz fundamental frequency. Different parameters setting for Class-F and Class-F⁻¹ are bias control, input power and load impedances synthesis for achievement the best tradeoff among gain, efficiency and

power. Bias condition for Class-F⁻¹ should be chosen to minimize the second harmonic component. Therefore, the bias voltage is typically set to the class-A bias point to allow the device a high output power with large signal gain. Class-F PA bias point decreases toward Class-B mode to increase the efficiency. As the quiescent current reduces, the shaping effects on harmonic components will be stronger.

In the second step, series-tuned resonators have been used in input and output matching networks to transfer the desired impedances and suppress the unwanted harmonics. The fundamental and harmonic impedances are set at the extrinsic of the device in such a way, the device sees the optimum impedances at the intrinsic. The distributed Harmonic Control Circuit (HCC) at the output of Class-F PA provides an open-circuited condition at the third harmonic and short-circuited at the second harmonic, while HCC at the input acts as a low pass filter with the purpose of preventing the delivery of harmonic power to the load. Similarly, in the inverse Class-F PA, HCC is optimized by nearly short termination of third harmonic and very high impedance of second harmonic at the device output. This means that the current and voltage are related to each other by varying the fundamental and harmonic terminations.

Fig. 3. Class-F PA schematic with HCC.

Because of internal parasitic components, the HCC in the schematic of Class-F/F⁻¹, is commonly placed prior to the fundamental matching network shown in Fig. 3, and generates reactance to control the harmonics. In practice, usually the HCC is conducted up to the third order harmonic, since the higher order harmonics increases the implementation difficulty and limits the efficiency improvement. The commercial packaged of GaN HEMT circuit model, has nonlinear effects originated by parasitic components. These nonlinear effects can degrade the efficiency, when it becomes a part of output matching network to see the intrinsic drain impedance.

Fig. 4. Harmonic spectrum of Class-F at 3.6GHz

The output spectrum of the Class-F PA up to fifth harmonics has been shown in Fig.4. The wave-shaping network acts as a filter to suppress down the third harmonic

power to -30dBm while passing the fundamental signal without loss. Therefore, the functionality of HCC has been confirmed since the fundamental and third harmonics are presented at the drain.

Fig. 5. Fourier voltage and current voltage waveforms of Class-F PA with three harmonics (a)Drain current (b)Drain voltage.

We have simulated the designed Class-F/ F^{-1} amplifiers and the results are shown in Fig. 5 and 6. The drain current and voltage waveform of Class-F PA are plotted in Fig. 5. The in-phase combination of fundamental and second harmonic shapes the drain current to be half- sinusoidal when a small portion of it goes below zero by reason of drain-source capacitance. Also, the out of phase combination of fundamental and third harmonic shapes the voltage waveform similar to a rectangular wave, where the third harmonic current component is significantly suppressed.

Fig. 6. Fourier voltage and current voltage waveforms of Class- F^{-1} PA with three harmonics (a)Drain current (b)Drain voltage.

Whereas, in Class- F^{-1} in Fig. 6, the amount of the generate third harmonic flattens the drain current waveform at the maximum current values and sharpens it at the minimum current values. Moreover, the time-domain waveforms are not perfect half sinusoidal for voltage and square wave for current and their deviation from ideal waveforms is due to the absence of higher-order harmonics.

Fig. 7. Simulation Results of output power, Gain, PAE and drain efficiency of Class F versus input power(w), (a) Class-F (b) Class- F^{-1}

The simulation results of gain flatness, drain efficiency and PAE under the same drain bias condition of Class-F and Class- F^{-1} are presented in Fig.7(a, b) respectively. Class-F PA, delivers lower gain than Class- F^{-1} PA due to the reduced

bias point. A small signal transducer power gain of Class- F^{-1} amplifier is flat at around 15dB. However, the gain flatness of Class-F PA is approximated at 9dB. Therefore, the inverse Class-F is suitable for low voltage amplifiers by extending output voltage swing. This extension can be seen in Class-F current waveform, however, it is limited by boundary of maximum current. Class- F^{-1} amplifier has superior PAE to the class-F. The former shows 54% PAE at input power of 30dBm which is 52% for the latter at input power of 33dBm.

The most striking outcome is the higher peak drain efficiency of Class-F PA in compared with Class- F^{-1} PA. Class-F shows maximum drain efficiency of 70% at 40.23dBm output power which is 10% higher than that of Class- F^{-1} PA at 40.57dBm output power. The lower drain efficiency of Class- F^{-1} is due to the breakdown voltage effects of the transistor, which generates current in the high voltage levels.

IV. OPERATION PRINCIPLE OF THE SATURATED DOHERTY AMPLIFIER

In many complex constellation schemes, the major issue associated with switching mode PAs is the introduced nonlinearity distortion as a result of operating into deep saturated condition. One of the most effective initiative to reduce the bit error rate produced by amplifier, is to combine additional advanced circuit to harness its performance across the dynamic power level. The linear operation principle of Doherty PA has been described well in literature [8]. The Doherty PA based on the active load modulation is implemented by carrier and peaking device stages. Since the overall efficiency of DPA depends on the maximum achievable efficiency by these two stages, employing Class-F/ F^{-1} as carrier and peaking devices can enable DPA for smart manufacturing application by providing highly linear and efficient operation.

Fig. 8. Schematic diagram of the saturated Doherty amplifier

The Schematic diagram of asymmetric Class-F/ F^{-1} DPA is shown in Fig. 8. It is composed of HCC, uneven power divider, offset lines for compensating the output parasitic effects of the transistors, output combiner to ensure in-phase combination of output currents at saturation. Besides, a phase compensation network at the input of peaking PA is employed to mitigate the phase variation and delay. Fig. 9, shows the load modulation behavior of Class-F/ F^{-1} DPA in which the carrier impedance is modulated by current supplied of peaking amplifier through the quarter-wave length transmission line.

The load seen by carrier PA can be changed while the voltage swing across it is constant resulting in the efficiency improvement. It is assumed that both amplifiers are linear function of the input voltage, in a manner, the constant voltage waveform of carrier terminal can be transformed into a constant current at the peaking terminal, without considering the load value.

Fig. 9. Equivalent circuit of the saturated Doherty amplifier.

The current and voltage of carrier and peaking PAs in proportion with the input voltage in three power levels are shown in Fig.10. At low power level, the fundamental load seen by the Class-F⁻¹carrier PA is terminated by twice of optimum load in order to experience the maximum efficiency at 6dB back-off output power and Class-F peaking PA is turned-off and modulated by a high impedance.

Fig. 10. The Carrier and Peaking current and voltage vs input drive voltage.

As the input power increases above $V_{turn\ on}$ of peaking PA which is set at the middle range, the carrier PA in saturation mode generates a square wave current and a half rectified voltage waveforms and increases the efficiency indeed. In this region, the peaking PA starts to conduct current into the output load that causes the degradation of impedance seen by carrier PA due to the impedance inverter.

Fig. 11. Simulated results of, Gain, PAE, drain efficiency and output power of Class-F/F⁻¹ DPA and conventional DPA versus input power

At the voltage between $V_{turn\ on}$ and V_{max} , the carrier PA acts as a constant voltage source while the efficiency of peaking PA raises as a consequence of optimal load modulation and maximum voltage swing. Finally, the peaking PA goes to compression at the maximum power level. The Class-F/F⁻¹ DPA and conventional DPA using ADS (Keysight) were designed and simulated at 3.6GHz in order to compare the

large signal performance. The simulation results of PAE, drain efficiency and gain versus input power is plotted in Fig.11, for (a) Class-F/F⁻¹ DPA and (b) Class B/C DPA. The results clearly reveal that saturated DPA exploits a drain efficiency of 65% at maximum output power of 43.58dBm and provides a 50% PAE at 8dB OBO while the conventional one delivers 46% at 6dB OBO.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the beneficial application of the voltage and current waveforms engineering, by generating optimum impedance conditions. We have analyzed and compared the time varying waveforms of the Class-F and inverse Class-F amplifiers. It is shown that the Class-F PA has higher drain efficiency, although larger gain-compression and higher output power and smaller output impedance have been achieved by the inverse Class-F. Also, we have discussed the dynamic load modulation technique using HCC allows to compensate the large power ratio between two stages and restore the appropriate load modulation of conventional Doherty PA. The simulated results confirmed that Class-F/F⁻¹ DPA has potential for exploiting complex modulation standards.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement H2020-MSCA-ITN-2016-SECRET-722424. This work is supported by the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER), through the Competitiveness and Internationalization Operational Programme (COMPETE 2020), Regional Operational Program of the Algarve (2020), Fundação para a ciência e Tecnologia; i-Five: Extensão do acesso de espectro dinâmico para rádio 5G, POCI-01-0145-FEDER-030500

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